

CoSTAR Network response

Copyright and Artificial Intelligence Consultation

February 2025

Introduction to the CoSTAR Network

CoSTAR¹ is a £75.6million investment delivered by the Arts and Humanities Research Council, the first substantial investment made in a national infrastructure for the creative industries. It will function as the UK's R&D network for creative technologies. The network is formed of five labs, based across the UK and bringing together leading technology and creative industries partners to drive innovation in emerging technologies across screen, games, performance and digital entertainment. The CoSTAR Network as a whole has an interdisciplinary, applied R&D focus on the future of advanced media production.

The CoSTAR Network's response to this consultation is underpinned by a shared commitment to inform and support the Government's ongoing efforts to drive new and innovative approaches to innovation in the AI and creative industries sectors, and to develop robust licensing and copyright mechanisms.

As a Network operating in the interests of both creative industries and technology companies, and those working across both of these growth sectors identified in the Government's Industrial Strategy Green Paper, we do not believe that the implementation of a TDM exception is the most likely to meet the Government's objectives. We do however support the importance of trust and transparency as stated under Option 3.

Response contributors and consultees

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Do you agree that option 3 - a data mining exception which allows right holders to reserve their rights, supported by transparency measures - is most likely to meet the objectives set out above?

No.

The AI Opportunities Action Plan published in January proposes a central question in its approach: “does this benefit the people and organisations trying to do new and ambitious things in the UK?”² We work with many of these organisations across the UK’s creative technology ecosystem, where creative and technology innovators work together to build creative-led, equitable and sustainable products and services that incentivise creators and technologists alike. References to innovation in the consultation refer only to the potential and risk of stalling the growth of AI innovation; the term ‘innovation’ is referenced 17 times in the consultation and 12 of these instances are focused solely on AI innovation. There is only one mention of musicians and artists undertaking technical innovation in their work and a recognition that the sectors must innovate together in partnership.³

We would highlight the significant contributions the creative industries already play in R&D and innovation, particularly technological innovation. The creative industries sector makes up 6% of the UK economy⁴ (more than AI at present), contributing £124bn in GVA⁵ – with many companies already working with AI (to take one example, 62% of videogames studios in the UK are using AI across their workflows)⁶. Any approach to innovation should foster mutual growth and benefit (not just on the side of those building large-scale AI platforms, many of which are not based in the UK), should consider long-term impact and be future facing. The impact of the proposed opt-out approach should consider the potentially negative impact it is likely to have on the long-term growth of the creative industries and innovation in the sector (which is underpinned by the production of IP and content). The law should determine and enforce copyright and not be decided by technology companies alone.

We believe that if the UK gets this right, we could become a world leader in innovative and creative-led approaches to technology innovation –incentivising inward investment into UK creative content from the largest AI players and fostering collaboration to grow small, UK AI players developing models responsibly and equitably.

Incentivising innovation, providing certainty and rewarding human creativity will come from an approach that does not assume that creative IP is there to be accessed for GAI training, but instead creates innovation opportunities to create new licensing and standardization models that are likely to drive shared growth across the creative industries and tech sectors, underpinned by robust licensing and remuneration models. Work being undertaken across the CoSTAR Network could assist in identifying these opportunities, mapping the evidence base to underpin new interventions, piloting programmes and identifying challenge partners.

All options require a clear technology roadmap and indicative/operational protection, and public innovation will play a critical role in enabling certainty, clarity and ease of access for both copyright holders and AI companies. Current solutions, such as robots.txt are not robust or nuanced enough in the current technological age, and do not allow copyright holders control over when their work is excluded/included and on what terms. A public innovation tool or solution should be designed in order for copyright holders to be easily identified and easily able to protect their IP, consent to use of their work and outline all benefits/terms for use of work in order to make well informed decisions and foster innovation-led collaboration. The CoSTAR Network, as the UK’s R&D Network for creative technology, could support in the development of roadmaps and piloting activity that can then be

² [AI Opportunities Action Plan - GOV.UK](#)

³ Ibid.

⁴ [How much does the UK invest in publicly supported R&D in the Creative Industries? And how does this compare to other sectors? – CRAIC](#)

⁵ [Creative industries add £124bn of value to UK - The Creative Industries](#)

⁶ [2024 Unity Gaming Report - Trends, data & expert tips | Unity](#)

scaled up. The Network is developing guidance for businesses to engage with technology innovation across multiple technology areas (AI, XR, future networks, virtual production and realtime).

We believe that in order for the UK to be a world-leading AI-maker, it needs to maintain its global leadership as an IP-maker – both of new responsible products and services, as well as creative content and software IP. A proposed “opt-out” TDM exception is likely to stifle this. Creators and creative companies, 90% of which are small companies in the UK, are unlikely to have the capacity/resources to implement opt out to multiple AI companies as there is no broad reaching, standardised approach to doing so (unless opting out across multiple platforms). In instances where companies do not “opt-out,” there are no obvious benefits or remuneration opportunities for the use of their IP. Companies need incentives in order to want to provide their IP for technology innovation that does not immediately involve or benefit them (e.g. why should I agree to this? What is the benefit for me and my company? How is my work being used, and what is it being used for?). Meanwhile, the balance falls strongly in favour of AI developers, where the benefits are immediately evident. In addition, given the rate of change in business practices, it is often unclear who the copyright owner is without extensive due diligence, with many creative outputs being “orphan works” where the copyright holder is not immediately obvious or known. We cannot presume to give AI companies this content without copyright holders being able to provide consent, nor without a robust and workable framework for doing so.

The past 20 years has seen the unequivocal growth of a handful of technology companies, particularly those operating social media platforms, and “walled garden” approaches, where huge amounts of data are held in the hands of a select few (predominantly US and China based) companies. An “opt out” model is likely to see a repeat of this model, where only a handful of companies benefit from huge swathes of data without any revenue flowing back to the creators of that data. Despite this, social media users still broadly “opt in” to handing data over to these firms for use of their services and being issued T&Cs. Opt out approaches are the equivalent of companies having immediate access to all content without any immediate benefits for the creators of that content.

To most benefit the UK, we feel that current copyright law could be expanded to both better reflect the digital turn (copyright based on print model is now outdated) and drive broader-reaching innovation across multiple sectors; this should be underpinned by benefits to UK growth sectors, including the creative industries. It should be noted that “AI” is not a sector⁷, but a tool that requires use and development across sector application areas, including the creative industries.

This could operate through a model akin to “opt in”, where licensing of content is dependent on clear instruction from the copyright holder, who would be given choices, outlined benefits and conditions of use, and where long term revenue is clear and agreed by all parties. This is likely to be the most effective and least disruptive mechanism, modifying existing copyright mark asserting ownership, but allowing for training if the rights holder makes an informed choice to consent (how IP will be used, why, how, what for etc) and is remunerated.

Which option do you prefer and why?

Maintaining and strengthening existing copyright law, whilst updating it to respond readily to the digital turn and the AI age, would be the most beneficial way of growing both the creative and technology sectors in partnership. In which case, an option akin to “opt in” would be our preference; as such, Option 1: strengthen copyright requiring licensing in all cases (with consent of the rights holder) – whilst maintaining current protocol of enabling access to materials for TDM for research (and not commercial) purposes would be our preferable option. This also reflects broad-ranging engagement we have had with creative industries and technology sector stakeholders. The option

⁷ This notion was supported by a member of the CoSTAR Foresight board.

states that it could “include clarifying existing legislation to provide legal certainty in how copyright law operates with AI models in the UK” and “provide[s] a clear route to remuneration for creators.”

As previously stated, we believe that if the UK gets this right, we could become a world leader in innovative and creative-led approaches to technology innovation – incentivising inward investment into UK creative content from the largest AI players and fostering collaboration to grow small, UK AI players developing models responsibly and equitably. Work being undertaken across the CoSTAR Network could assist in identifying these opportunities, mapping the evidence base to underpin new interventions, piloting programmes and identifying challenge partners.

An approach akin to “opt in” would mean that creators would be able to decide where and how their work is used, and incentivise AI companies to be more transparent about use of works. This would enable a more simple and universal process where creators can be in control of the distribution of their work, decide to “opt in”, and change their minds if they so wish. IP (and its associated revenue) is the lifeblood of the creative industries and the sector’s future growth, and could create a new model for driving inward investment into publicly owned UK databases, via the suggested National Data Library or otherwise.

Do you support the introduction of an exception along the lines outlined in section C of the consultation?

We believe that any approach, including an approach more akin to “opt in”, should be built robustly with technical roadmaps and pilots that foster collaborative and mutually beneficial approaches for AI and creative companies alike. The government should consider mechanisms through which to incentivise creators to produce IP, with the option of contributing to publicly-owned datasets including the proposed National Data Library. This could be through the funding and delivery of new pilots where promising AI start- and scale-ups work directly with creators to collaboratively develop new AI products and services powered by leading UK creative IP, working together to solve critical challenges and support government mission objectives.

This could be an area of growth and international leadership for the UK – and whilst differing from the approach taken by other territories, could lead to new mechanisms for inward investment into UK AI, creative and technology companies (the UK’s base of which are largely scale ups and SMEs) that are developed collaboratively, responsibly and ethically. For example, large US companies could purchase publicly owned datasets that are made up of the UK’s world-leading IP and new innovative approaches to licensing and standardisation could see the development of competitive global markets. This would also speak to the Government’s objectives of driving adoption of technologies; more sectors, including the creative industries, are likely to invest in and adopt technologies that they trust and that benefit them – this leads to an additional area of opportunity in driving adoption and diffusion of AI.

The AI Opportunities Action Plan recommendation of AI Growth Zones is a welcome proposition to boost innovation opportunity across regions in the UK. It is also an opportune mechanism through which to bring together innovators from across sectors to develop new solutions aligned to key mission areas and challenges. For example, challenge funding could be allocated to bring together companies and IP creators to create new datasets to drive the creation of competitive AI models and solutions, underpinned by innovative approaches to rights management, incentivising IP creators through royalties.

There is significant opportunity for the development of high-impact pilots working directly with the vast array of UK (as well as international partnerships of) creative technology and AI innovators to develop new prototypes relating to licensing, copyright and technological innovation. The CoSTAR Network, as the UK’s R&D Network for Creative Technology will work with innovators working directly in creative technologies and AI and ways to develop responsible and ethical approaches to AI innovation, and is eager to support the government’s efforts in this regard. This work is already embedded across Network activities, including enterprise and commercialisation programmes focussed on technical and business support, with particular emphasis on AI (1:2:1 mentorship to

work with and adopt tools such as GenerativeAI, mentorship and support for navigating current and proposed changes to legislation, AI ethics etc.)⁸ in addition the Network is mapping international approaches to AI legislation and trends in AI tool adoption and use across the UK.⁹

What action should a developer take when a reservation has been applied to a copy of a work?

The approach outlined as preferable in the consultation (opt out) is not a productive or viable long-term solution and is likely time consuming and significantly challenging for AI developers and creators alike: an individual company may opt out of TDM use for one company; that company may have several hundred individual requests to acknowledge, and then figure out ways of removing that creator's work from their model. The "opt out" approach only works on the basis that the system would be so time consuming and difficult to navigate that many rights holders will be put off doing so in the first place. We believe that this option is likely to hinder productivity and innovation, and will be hugely cost and time intensive. Creative businesses, too, would have to spend a significant amount of time opting out and this will have a huge long-term impact on the growth of the sector (time wasted and no benefit for doing so). "Opt out" will also be much harder to police (referring back to the earlier point regarding orphan works and oversight/governance challenges likely to emerge).

Instead, there should be a standardised roadmap and framework that enables creative collectives to sell and license IP to AI companies when they choose to do so, where AI companies are required to be transparent about how work will be used, and that incentivises creative companies to provide IP on a basis of shared benefit (e.g. royalties for the amount of time a work is used).

This could be ignited in the UK with new innovation pilots where creative, AI and creative technology companies collaborate to solve this challenge and develop new solutions – essentially driving a new market in the responsible licensing of creative IP. This could also include contributions to publicly owned datasets, built upon British values and creativity, that can be sold and licensed overseas. The UK has a unique competitive global advantage in this regard. The UK is unlikely to compete with the US/China when it comes to big-tech, and should rather support its small and scaling businesses and world-leading education institutes to develop new models and frameworks that can be harnessed and bought-into overseas. The goal should be to develop new and transformative public tools that will be resilient in the long-term.

What should be the legal consequences if a reservation is ignored?

Reservation should be assumed unless stated otherwise (something akin to opt-in) – if ignored, companies should have the right to take legal action (as we are already seeing in numerous global cases, including Getty Images vs Stability AI, Record Labels vs Udio, Authors Guild vs Open AI and others). Whilst large companies have the funds and capacity to manage legal proceedings when fostering a "move fast and break things"¹⁰ approach, growth would not be the outcome of small and promising companies going through these same disruptions. Long-term stability and consequent growth are more likely to be the outcome of an approach that is fair, benefits all involved, incentivises adoption and diffusion and remunerates effectively.

In addition, as stated in previous answers, tracking where reservations have been ignored in an "opt out" approach scenario will be incredibly difficult to keep on top of and put significant pressure on regulators to track compliance.

How can compliance with standards be encouraged?

Compliance should be the base expectation. Investment into IP for training purposes should be seen on the same footing as other investments AI companies might make in compute or GPUs. Through the lens of our response to this consultation, compliance can be encouraged by fostering a

⁸ [CoSTAR Access Programmes | CoSTAR](#)

⁹ [Foregrounding a creative-led approach to technology and AI innovation | CoSTAR](#)

¹⁰ [AI Opportunities Action Plan - GOV.UK](#)

clearer and mutually beneficial approach from the outset, underpinned by transparency. AI companies are more likely to comply if they know they will be able to access and license transformational IP that will enhance models, and where consent is given and thus having legal certainty. Compliance could also be encouraged through investment in publicly owned datasets, where the process of obtaining and working with the IP is cost/time efficient for all parties involved. In addition, licensing of IP for AI training could become a service that not only benefits AI companies (who get access to world leading IP and are therefore more likely to develop more targeted, interesting and less generic products) but rights holders too (a long-term revenue stream based on every time the work is used).

Does current practice relating to the licencing of copyright works for AI training meet the needs of creators and performers?

In theory the existing copyright regime works: if an AI company wants access to IP, it should obtain a license to use the IP under copyright law. However, this isn't currently happening and this is leading to significant disruption and numerous global court cases because of the factors identified in the consultation (lack of transparency; determining what can/can't be used; black boxed approaches). Existing copyright laws must cater for the digital turn. UK companies (both IP producers and AI companies) need clarity and incentives to work together and collaborate to pilot new approaches with mutual benefit.

Should the government have a role in encouraging collective licensing and/or data aggregation services? If so, what role should it play?

The Government should galvanise those with a stake in this field – it should play a role in ensuring transparency measures are put in place – and work closely with all stakeholders to develop a consistent and standardised approach to remuneration to not only lead the world with novel and responsible approaches, but to drive long-term growth and ensure time and cost efficiency in the short term. The Government should build consensus around what will work – and incentivise companies to be involved in the process of responding to this challenge (for example, R&D and innovation mechanisms to pilot activity that encourage collaboration and the development of solutions). The Government could also produce guidance and frameworks that would advise and guide companies to ensure measures are workable, working in collaboration with industry and academia to do so. Per previous answers, the CoSTAR Network could assist in identifying these opportunities and establishing guidance, mapping the evidence base to underpin new interventions, piloting programmes and identifying relevant partners.

Based on the suggested acceptance of recommendations made in the AI Opportunities Action Plan, the Government should also align other suggested mechanisms (including the proposed National Data Library) with any proposed legislative changes, and ensure that creative businesses are a critical part of these developments. There is a crucial role to play in incentivising the sector to bring its expertise into all innovation activity in this realm. In so doing, balance the scales to account for where successful innovation is already taking place (the creative industries have an existing track record and contribute significantly to the economy). This is opposed to further dividing sectors due to mistrust, lack of transparency, and making decisions without involving sectors involved in the development of workable solutions.

These efforts could be supported by the development of a new collecting body for Generative AI training licenses that would be specialised in this particular area and work alongside existing licensing bodies to remunerate rights holders.

Finally, the Government has a critical role to play in international partnership, collaboration, trade and inward investment. The UK could lead in specialist, challenge-led and mission-based approaches in this area that the rest of the world can invest in and adopt.

Do you agree that AI developers should disclose the sources of their training material?

Yes – this is the premise of any transparency measures. If developing a standardised rights management system, this should be built around enabling disclosure for the copyright holder. This should also be aligned to appropriate licensing and remuneration for creators. Suggested incentives outlined under q.24 on steps for Government to encourage AI development in the UK would be available for companies that conform to transparency and standards.

What steps can the government take to encourage AI developers to train their models in the UK and in accordance with UK law to ensure that rights of right holders are respected?

The UK's long-established strengths across both the creative industries and digital and technologies mean that these sectors in unison can be leveraged to stimulate international trade, fostering inward investment and solving shared challenges.

This could be enhanced through the development of new international incentives to drive global competitiveness, for example, embedding AI innovation readily in existing tax credits that cater for the unique contribution of the creative industries via IP and content. The UK could pioneer new partnerships focussed on this particular area of creative industries and AI innovation, working with other international creative industries leaders to develop, trial and test new transparency and licensing solutions.

The Government could develop a range of 'packages' that incentivise companies to train their models in the UK in accordance with UK law, the development of which could be piloted and supported by the CoSTAR Network. Such packages could be purchased when training models in the UK, including access to publicly owned IP datasets, access to data centres and infrastructure, potential tax credits or incentive systems that encourage development in UK, access to leading expertise and collaboration opportunities/plugin to universities and R&D activity, etc. Packages could be subsidised for UK companies depending on size and objectives and free for R&D. The UK could prioritise 'specialised' datasets as part of its National Data Library – garnering investment by reducing financial and legal uncertainty, with quality approaches underpinned by transparency and remuneration.

To drive competitiveness, the UK should also consider a suite of sovereign LLMs and SLMs; other countries are ahead in this regard (see Falcon UAE, GPT-SW3 Sweden and many others across the EU).¹¹

What other developments are driving emerging questions for the UK's copyright framework, and how should the government respond to them?

We must acknowledge the long-standing growth of the creative industries and its contribution to the UK economy. If IP creators cannot prevent their IP from being used to create derivative competitive works, there is likely to be a significant negative impact on the creative industries, the workforce, and current contribution to GDP. The sector is also a significant driver of technological innovation, leading to the development of new technology platforms and applications that are underpinned by safety, equity and responsibility. The UK must protect and continually invest in what we are good at – to ensure long term growth and innovation. The division between what the consultation refers to as the AI and creative industries sectors respectively, are not separate – but have effectively always overlapped. This context is central to UKRI's investment in the national CoSTAR Network, with its focus on the adoption of advanced and convergent technologies across the creative industries.

Whilst a structurally pillared approach to technologies and sectors provides a useful means for determining areas central to the Government's growth ambitions, it does not accurately reflect the way in which tools, products and services are developed, combining and integrating different

¹¹ See: [Falcon LLM: Abu Dhabi's Based TII Latest AI Breakthrough for Next-Gen Solutions](#); [GPT-SW3 | AI Sweden](#); [Home - Gaia-X Hub France](#)

technologies (also referred to as technological convergence) and the unique growth potential enabled by such convergence.

Such pillared approaches are subsequently reflected in innovation funding opportunities which tend to be separated by technology types and often unintentionally discourage cross-sector and convergent technology collaboration and development. It also means that many mechanisms are not interoperable across multiple technologies (in the context of this consultation, for example, how would new legislation around IP apply to the development of new immersive technologies like VR and AR?).

The creative industries accounts for 1% of UKRI funding despite making up a total of 6% of the UK economy. This is compounded by definitions adopted around R&D and innovation that tend to disincentivise the contribution of some creative sectors. For example, R&D definitions outlined for qualifying for tax credits apply to “activity recognised as scientific or technological innovation,” and might not include innovation in creative content and creative IP that fuels technological innovation. For example, the EPSRC funded XR Network+ programme is exploring how collaborative academic led research in virtual production and convergent media technologies that partners with industry can have an impact in next generation content creation and consumption and its spillover effects into the wider digital economy.¹² In addition, the DECADE programme is looking specifically at ways that Distributed Ledger Technology and blockchain solutions can be leveraged for the licensing and attribution of creative IP in the context of generative AI.¹³

Technology innovation and convergence reflects a high impact opportunity in the creative industries, incentivising the development of new products and solutions that crowd in around a problem space or mission area (e.g. IP, skills, infrastructure, adoption and diffusion, net zero etc) as opposed to an individual technology.

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¹² [Funding for research into virtual production - XR Network+](#)

¹³ [DECaDE | The Centre for the Decentralised Economy](#)